

Echoes: An Open RAN-enabled System for Indoors Localization Using Smart Surfaces

Pau Baguer¹, J. Xavier Salvat Lozano^{2, 3}, Guillermo Encinas Lago¹, Placido Mursia², Esteban Municio¹, Marco Rossanese², Vincenzo Sciancalepore², Xavier Costa-Perez^{1,2,4}

¹i2CAT Foundation, AI-Dirven Systems Group, Barcelona, 08034, Spain

²NEC Laboratories Europe, 6G Networks Group, Heidelberg, 69115, Germany

³UAB (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona), Department of Telecommunications and Systems Engineering, Bellaterra, 08193, Spain

⁴ICREA Foundation, Barcelona, 08010, Spain

This work was supported by the European Commission through Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking grants No. SNS-JU-101097083 (BeGREEN), SNS-JU-101139130 (6G-DISAC) and SNS-JU-101192521 (Multi-X), by the CDTI and the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR within the Call "Ayudas Cervera para Centros Tecnológicos 2023" under Grant 6G-DIFERENTE (CER-20231018) the European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR (Call UNICO I+D 5G 2021) under Grant TSI-063000-2021-7-Open6G and by the CERCA Programme.

ABSTRACT Indoor localization systems are poised to revolutionize mobile applications, enabling precise navigation, immersive augmented reality, and context-aware pervasive computing. Emerging 5G/6G Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) architectures offer a promising pathway for achieving accurate and ubiquitous indoor positioning driven by rapid technological advancements and standardization efforts (e.g., 3GPP). This paper presents *Echoes*, a novel system within the Open RAN (O-RAN) architecture that leverages smart surfaces for precise user positioning. *Echoes* improves current smart surfaces sensing systems inferring the received signal phase solely from power measurements of reference signals used to measure the uplink channel. *Echoes* achieves this by exploiting an inherent property of smart surfaces: steering configurations are not singular, and introducing a constant phase offset to all elements achieves the same intended reflection direction but with a different reflected phase. *Echoes* combines the sensed direction of a user with the angle of arrival estimation to estimate the position of a user in a sensing area. Our prototype, evaluated in a real-world indoor setting, exhibits a mean absolute user localization error (MAE) of 0.9 meters. These results highlight the potential of *Echoes* to provide robust and accurate indoor positioning for next-generation mobile applications.

INDEX TERMS Open RAN, Joint Communication and Sensing, Smart surface, Localization

I. Introduction

In recent years, there has been a surging interest in developing precise RF-based indoor localization systems that overcome the limitations of traditional systems, such as the Global Positioning System (GPS), which lacks reliable positioning in complex indoor settings. High-precision indoor localization has the potential to foster a wide range of applications, including indoor navigation, augmented reality, and location-aware pervasive computing [1]–[5]. Due to its increasing ubiquitous coverage, indoor positioning systems built on top of cellular 5G/6G networks have garnered significant attention from academia and industry because of their potential for jointly integrating precise positioning

services and communication [6]–[10], also known as the Joint Communication and Sensing (JCAS) paradigm.

Besides the opportunities brought by smart surfaces in communication systems—such as wireless coverage extension and efficient network coverage planning [11]–[15], which can be specifically tailored towards improving outdoors positioning performance [16]—they have also emerged as a promising building block for next-generation indoor positioning systems. As they allow for controlling the reflection properties of impinging electromagnetic signals—effectively generating a reflected signal, motivating the name of our solution, *Echoes*—they can be used to sense the direction or position of users in a sensing area [5], [17]–[21]. Sensing systems built on top of smart surfaces allow for

FIGURE 1: Best received power gain (dB) measured using different codebook configurations with a 10×10 smart surface.

further exploiting JCAS by extracting location information using communication signals reflected by the smart surface. Current indoor positioning solutions using smart surfaces estimate user locations by dynamically probing different reflection configurations from a pre-computed/pre-calibrated codebook, searching for configurations that maximize the gain of the received communication signal [5], [22]–[25].

However, current approaches face several critical challenges that hinder their performance and scalability. (1) **Reduced resolution:** In an indoor scenario, smart surfaces tend to be smaller due to space constraints, yielding a broader beam for steering reflected waves into specific directions, especially in sub-6GHz frequencies. Also, the reliance on far-field assumptions when using a smart surface (i.e., the receiver has to be placed more than $\frac{2D^2}{\lambda}$ away, where D is the diagonal size of the smart surface and λ the wavelength) and the limited functional angle ranges (see § 5 for more details on smart surface’s functional angle ranges) results in a small search space, which yields poor spatial resolution. We address this challenge by introducing additional sources of information, such as the angle of arrival at the small cell. (2) **Smart surface low-gain contributions:** Small to medium-sized open indoor spaces (e.g., an office, a smart factory, a VR gaming environment, etc.) might not degrade electromagnetic waves significantly, which leaves small gain changes when combining the power contribution of the smart surface’s reflected signal with the direct path. Such small gain changes impair our ability to identify the smart surface beam against the baseline power level. This phenomenon does not reduce the received power, but it introduces significant inaccuracy and outliers to any estimation of user’s location. Our approach mitigates noisy samples by prioritizing high-gain smart surface configurations and fitting several collected data points to sinusoidal functions, effectively bypassing outliers. (3) **Phase misalignment:** As the reflected signal and the direct path signal may not have an optimal phase alignment, finding the optimal smart surface configuration only guarantees the estimation of the user direction as the phase of the wave repeats itself every wavelength λ . The proposed algorithm computes the phase misalignment at the receiver (small cell) and utilizes it as an

extra source of information to determine the user’s direction. Consequently, we turn this challenge of most smart surface-based positioning algorithms into an opportunity.

To illustrate the previous challenges, consider the scenario depicted in Fig. 2 where we want to sense a user in the open space with area $d_s \times d_s$. Fig. 2a depicts the lateral view, and Fig. 2b depicts the zenithal view. We have placed a smart surface and a small cell on opposite walls at the same height h . We also left a space d between the smart surface and the sensed area so that the area’s limits fall within the limit operating angles of the smart surface along the azimuth axis.

To illustrate challenge (1), we consider an open space of $d_s = 10\text{m}$ (i.e., 100m^2) with a smart surface and a small cell centered at a height of $h = 2\text{m}$ and $d = 2.9\text{m}$. Using a smart surface like the one in [26] (a $40\text{cm} \times 40\text{cm}$ board) with 10° of Half Power Beamwidth (HPBW) and a functional range between $\theta \in [-60^\circ, 60^\circ]$ and $\phi \in [-45^\circ, 45^\circ]$ in the azimuth and elevation axis, respectively, it is feasible to probe configurations every 5° . On the azimuth axis we can probe a total of 23 configurations, i.e., $\{-55^\circ, -50^\circ, \dots, 50^\circ, 55^\circ\}$, while in the elevation axis we can probe only 3 configurations: $\{-15^\circ, -20^\circ, -25^\circ\}$. Thus, we have an azimuth resolution of 0.43m , and an elevation resolution of 3.3m .

To illustrate challenges (2) and (3), we probe all possible configurations of a smart surface codebook (see § 5), setting up a transmitter and a receiver in two different positions and measuring the received power gain. Fig. 1a shows the received power gain that the previously mentioned smart surface [26] introduces in an indoor open environment for different values of azimuth and elevation (see § B for the details of our smart surface and testbed). We can see how the best and worst improvement in dB is within -1.61 dB to 1.05 dB . Also, notice that we cannot observe a clear direction (θ, ϕ) that maximizes the received power gain. In an indoor environment with good coverage from an access point, it is key to align the phase of the reflected signal with the phase of the main path (see § 4). Fig. 1a shows the results when aligning the phase of the reflected signal with the phase of the main path signal. Now, gains are between -0.07 dB and 1.55 dB . Since gains are small, noise can easily be introduced in sensing the direction of a user. Furthermore, aligning the phase of the reflected signal enables us to find the potential direction of the user, but not its position.

Fig. 2a and 2b also depict a solution to the previous challenges, which is estimating the angle of arrival (Θ_u^h, Θ_u^v) of a user with the small cell and combining it with the sensed user direction using the smart surface (θ_u^R, ϕ_u^R) . However, current 5G/6G cellular systems do not expose phase measurements of received radio signals [27], rendering the estimation of Θ_u^h and Θ_u^v difficult. Furthermore, high-precision angle of arrival estimation requires the processing of I/Q samples of high bandwidth signals to capture fine-grained phase details [28], [29].

The previously mentioned problems call for innovative solutions for improving the indoor location-based systems

FIGURE 2: Example scenario.

based on smart surfaces on top of future cellular systems. In this paper, we present *Echoes*, an indoor location system that leverages the flexibility of future mobile systems based on Open RAN (O-RAN) architectures and the reconfiguration capabilities of smart surfaces. *Echoes* improves current smart surface sensing systems, estimating the angle of arrival between a cellular device and the small cell. *Echoes* leverages the periodic uplink reference signals sent by users and the smart surfaces' reconfiguration capabilities to estimate the angle of arrival (AoA) $\hat{\Theta}_u^h$ and $\hat{\Theta}_u^v$, as shown in fig. 2. In combination with the smart surface reflection direction that maximizes the received gain *Echoes* localizes a user within a sensing area. *Echoes* leverages the following key features:

- **O-RAN radio metrics:** The O-RAN architecture enables access to real-time network metrics through its E2 interface. This allows for the collection of key metrics [27], [30]. Our system leverages these metrics to estimate the AoA while reconfiguring a smart surface. Specifically, we utilize the standard E2SM-KPM (Key Performance Measurement) service model to acquire the Uplink Reference Signal Received Power (UL-RSRP) measurements directly from the 5G-NR base station via an xApp. Furthermore, we employ a dApp for low-latency decentralized smart surface control. Overall, this eliminates the need for extensive modifications to the 5G RAN software when integrating *Echoes*.
- **Smart surfaces' reflected wave phase:** A unique property of smart surfaces is that a configuration reflecting waves toward a specific direction is not singular. Applying the same phase shift offset value to all configuration elements achieves the same reflection angle, changing the phase of the reflected wave. This flexibility allows smart surfaces to tailor the phase of reflected signals without altering their direction, enabling advanced control over wave interference and enabling AoA estimation between a user and a small cell using power measurement metrics.

In summary, this paper makes the following contributions:

FIGURE 3: O-RAN architecture

- We present *Echoes*, an indoor localization system that improves current positioning systems using smart surfaces. It estimates the angle of arrival between users and the access point by controlling the phase shift offset in the smart surface and does not require the processing of I/Q samples.
- We experimentally confirm *Echoes*' performance in a real indoor setting through a complete deployment of the system architecture
- We anchor *Echoes* in a point of the O-RAN design space, proposing a novel use-case driven smart surface integration into O-RAN that includes smart surface control procedures.

II. Background

We first briefly provide background information required to understand *Echoes*, including a primer on O-RAN and its interfaces (§ A), an overview of the uplink 5G-NR signal used to measure the uplink channel (§ B), a comprehensive review on smart surfaces (§ C) and a summary on angle of arrival estimation (§ D).

A. Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN)

Nowadays, cellular networks are experiencing a transformative shift in their design and functionality. Led by the O-RAN Alliance, future mobile networks will feature an architecture that is built on disaggregated software components, open interfaces, and programmable hardware [31].

O-RAN splits the base station's functionalities into three distinct units: (i) a Central Unit (CU), (ii) a Distributed Unit (DU), and (iii) a Radio Unit (RU) (referred to as O-CU, O-DU, and O-RU, respectively, in O-RAN parlance). The O-CU is further split into two components for the Control Plane (CP) and the User Plane (UP). All components of the O-RAN architecture but the O-RU, can be deployed on a hybrid cloud computing platform known as O-Cloud. The O-Cloud comprises a pool of heterogeneous computing resources and virtualization infrastructure combined across one or more physical data centers.

1) O-RAN Radio Intelligent Controllers (RICs)

O-RAN introduces the idea of RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), which enables control and monitoring of the RAN via software applications, thereby fulfilling the vision of fully automated self-organizing networks. O-RAN specifies two RICs, which operate at different timescales, namely the non-Real-Time RIC (non-RT RIC), which operates at scales of hundreds of milliseconds to seconds or minutes (i.e., 100ms - 1s), and the near-Real-Time RIC (near-RT RIC), which operates at scales of tens of milliseconds to hundreds of milliseconds (10ms - 100ms). The non-RT RIC hosts software applications known as rApps for long-term data-driven optimization and policy coordination using interfaces such as the A1 interface. The near-RT RIC applies the policies received from the non-RT RIC and hosts xApps, applications for low-latency control and monitoring of the RAN components over the E2 interface. More recently, O-RAN has witnessed the proposal of dApps—customized, distributed applications designed to go beyond the capabilities of xApps and rApps by enabling RAN intelligence directly at the CUs and DUs for real-time use cases [32], [33]. It is envisioned that dApps will be implemented by extending the E2 interface. Fig. 3 shows the different O-RAN components, including the RICs and dApps, along with their related interfaces and reconfiguration timescales.

2) E2 interface

The E2 interface interconnects the near-RT RIC and the E2 nodes. E2 nodes comprise the disaggregated network functions O-CU-CP, O-CU-UP, and O-DU of a gNB and O-RAN-compliant LTE eNBs. The E2 interface enables radio resource control and monitoring functionalities of the RAN. The metrics collection from the RAN can either be triggered on a scheduled basis or by predefined events. These control and data collection processes target different levels, such as individual cells, network slices, or specific UEs. The E2 interface is organized into: (i) the E2 Application Protocol (E2AP), which coordinates the communication between the near-RT RIC and E2 nodes (e.g., Setup, Indication, Reset, etc.), and (ii) the E2 Service Model (E2SM), which implements services of specific RAN functions, such as reporting RAN metrics or adjusting RAN configuration parameters. Each E2 node exposes a set of supported RAN functions, representing the services and capabilities it supports.

B. 5G-NR Sounding Reference Signal (SRS)

In 5G-NR, user equipment devices (UEs) periodically transmit the Sounding Reference Signal (SRS) on the uplink, allowing the serving gNB to estimate the quality of the channel at different frequencies. SRS are periodically transmitted as often as every 2nd subframe (2 ms) or as infrequently as every 16th frame (160ms). The SRS is transmitted on the last symbol of the subframe. Based on the received power measurements from the uplink SRS, the serving gNB

FIGURE 4: Smart surface coordinate system.

schedules uplink transmissions on resource blocks of good quality. Open-RAN supports monitoring the values of the received power of the SRS [30], [34]. It supports measuring them periodically for the different UEs and antennas in the serving gNB.

C. A primer on Smart Surfaces

Smart surfaces, also called Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs), are innovative structures designed to alter the behaviour of impinging radio waves without requiring complex RF chains. A smart surface board is usually arranged as a planar antenna array with $N = N_i \times N_j$ unit cells (e.g., patch antennas) separated by a fixed sub-wavelength distance $\delta = \frac{\lambda}{2}$. We index any unit cell in the n_i -th row and the n_j -th column as $n = n_i + n_j \cdot N_j, \forall n_i \in \{0, 1, \dots, N_i - 1\}, n_j \in \{0, 1, \dots, N_j - 1\}$. A smart surface's unit cell induces a phase shift of value $\psi_n \in [0, 2\pi]$ to an impinging radio wave. The different phase shifts applied by the unit cells steer the reflected wave towards a specific direction. Fig. 4 depicts the conceptual design of a smart surface.

1) Board reference

Fig. 4 depicts the reference coordinate system for a smart surface used throughout this paper. We measure the azimuth (θ) and elevation angle (ϕ) for any impinging or reflected wave using a horizontal coordinate system. We measure the azimuth angle from the right side (i.e., from the purple dashed line in Fig. 4) to the left side of the board in the range of $\theta \in [180^\circ, 360^\circ]$. Similarly, we measure the elevation angle from the normal direction (i.e., from the white dashed line in Fig. 4) to either the upper or lower side of the board reference. Thus, $\phi \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$. Note that by setting $\theta = 270^\circ$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$ we have the direction normal to the board.

2) Reflection model

We denote as $\Phi \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ a diagonal matrix $\Phi = \text{diag}(e^{-j\psi_1}, \dots, e^{-j\psi_N})$ with ψ_n describing the phase shift applied by the n -th unit cell. We also denote as $\mathbf{a}_R(\theta_t, \phi_t) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ the array response vector of the smart surface for an impinging radio wave coming from the direction θ_t and ϕ_t

along the azimuth and elevation, respectively. Similarly, we denote as $\mathbf{a}_R^H(\theta_r, \phi_r) \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times N}$ the array response vector which steers a reflected wave towards the direction θ_r and ϕ_r . An element n of $\mathbf{a}_R(\theta, \phi)$ can be computed using the steering vector model as:

$$\{\mathbf{a}_R(\theta, \phi)\}_{n=0}^{N-1} = e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\delta n_i \cos \theta} e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\delta n_j \sin \phi} \quad (1)$$

where $n_i = n \bmod N_j$, $n_j = \frac{n-n_i}{N_j}$ and $\delta = \lambda/2$. Assuming far-field conditions, a transmit signal x impinging from the direction (θ_t, ϕ_t) and reflecting towards the direction (θ_r, ϕ_r) can be modeled as:

$$\begin{aligned} y_r &= \mathbf{a}_R^H(\theta_r, \phi_r) \Phi \mathbf{a}_R(\theta_t, \phi_t) x \\ &= \left(\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{-j\psi_n} e^{j\pi n_i (\cos \theta_t - \cos \theta_r)} \cdot e^{j\pi n_j (\sin \phi_t - \sin \phi_r)} \right) x. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

3) Steering configuration

From previous Eq. (2) we can derive the optimal phase shifts that a smart surface's unit cells should apply to reflect an incoming signal from (θ_t, ϕ_t) towards (θ_r, ϕ_r) . To maximize y_r , the smart surface needs to compensate for the phase difference between the impinging and reflected signal as:

$$-\psi_n + \pi n_i (\cos \theta_t - \cos \theta_r) + \pi n_j (\sin \phi_t - \sin \phi_r) = 0 \quad (3)$$

Modeling the smart surface configuration with the steering vector model, the phase shift ψ_n of each unit cell n can be expressed as:

$$e^{j\psi_n} = e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\delta n_i \cos \theta_n} \cdot e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\delta n_j \sin \phi_n}. \quad (4)$$

Substituting (4) in (3) yields:

$$\theta_n = \arccos(\cos \theta_t - \cos \theta_r) \quad (5)$$

$$\phi_n = \arcsin(\sin \phi_t - \sin \phi_r). \quad (6)$$

Note that θ_n and ϕ_n do not depend on the n index of a unit cell. Also, the difference between $\cos \theta_t - \cos \theta_r$ and $\sin \phi_t - \sin \phi_r$ should lie in $[-1, 1]$ so that $\theta_n, \phi_n \in \mathbb{R}$. The reflected signal y_r equals $y_r = Nx$ when the smart surface reflects an impinging radio wave optimally.

4) Offset configuration

From Eq. (2) we can also observe that the smart surface's unit cell configurations are not singular. Indeed, if we apply a phase shift offset ψ_0 to all ψ_n , i.e., $\psi'_n = \psi_n + \psi_0$, we still maximize the power of y_r although we are changing its phase. Indeed, the new reflected signal y'_r equals to $y'_r = e^{-j\psi_0} y_r$.

FIGURE 5: Angle of Arrival (AoA) estimation in the small cell. The cone-shaped surfaces represent the set of possible directions from which the user signal could arrive, as determined by a pair of antennas on the small cell.

5) Codebook computation

To navigate the possible combinations of unit cells' phase shift configurations, it is a common practice to compute a configuration codebook, which is a set $\mathcal{C} = \{\mathbf{C}_k\}$, where $|\mathcal{C}| = K$, of precomputed phase shifts configurations that allow steering an incident wave towards a specific direction. Codebook configurations $\mathbf{C}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_i \times N_j}$ are generated by discretizing a range of values for θ_n and ϕ_n . Let $\mathcal{P} = \{\theta_0, \dots, \theta_{P-1}\}$, where $|\mathcal{P}| = P$, be a finite set of possible azimuth values and let $\mathcal{Q} = \{\phi_0, \dots, \phi_{Q-1}\}$, where $|\mathcal{Q}| = Q$, be also a finite set of possible elevation values. The set $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q} = \{(\theta_0, \phi_0), (\theta_0, \phi_1), \dots, (\theta_{P-1}, \phi_{Q-1})\}$, where $|\mathcal{P}| \cdot |\mathcal{Q}| = K$, contains all possible combinations of the azimuth and elevation values of the codebook \mathcal{C} .

A configuration \mathbf{C}_k applies to each of the smart surface's unit cells a phase shift ψ_n using the k -th element pair of azimuth and elevation values (θ_p, ϕ_q) from the set $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$. The individual phase shift ψ_n of a unit cell n (i.e., the (n_i, n_j) unit cell) is computed as the phase of the complex value using Eq. (4). That is:

$$\psi_n = \angle \left(e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\delta n_i \cos \theta_p} \cdot e^{j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\delta n_j \sin \phi_q} \right). \quad (7)$$

As reported for other state-of-the-art smart surfaces, azimuth and elevation ranges for the codebook are limited due to hardware constraints. For instance, [26] reports operating configurations within the range $\theta_p \in [-60^\circ, 60^\circ]$ and $\phi_q \in [-45^\circ, 45^\circ]$.

Furthermore, we denote as $\mathbf{C}_k(\psi_0)$ the configuration obtained by applying an offset ψ_0 to the configuration \mathbf{C}_k , as introduced in § 4. Note that the diagonal matrix Φ , which contains all the phase shifts applied by each unit cell, depends on the configuration \mathbf{C}_k applied in the smart surface as $\Phi(\mathbf{C}_k(\psi_0))$.

D. Angle of arrival estimation

AoA measurement is a technique used to determine the direction from which an RF signal reaches an antenna array. This method consists of evaluating the differences in path lengths experienced by different antennas at the receiving

FIGURE 6: Echoes' scenario.

array. Fig. 5 illustrates a basic setup where a far-field emitter (TX) transmits a narrowband signal s to a two-element antenna array (RX). The antenna array may be oriented in the horizontal direction (Fig. 5a) with the TX oriented at an angle of Θ_h from the array axis, or in the vertical direction (Fig. 5b) with the TX oriented at an angle of Θ_v from the array axis. As shown in both figures, the path difference d can be computed as $d = \frac{\lambda}{2} \sin(\Theta)$. Since the antennas are separated by $\frac{\lambda}{2}$, using the triangle inequality, $d \leq \frac{\lambda}{2}$. Moreover, a wave traveling an extra distance d changes its phase by an amount $\Delta\varphi = 2\pi\frac{d}{\lambda}$, which is equal to the phase difference between the signal s arriving at antenna A_0 , and the signal s arriving at the antenna A_1 , i.e., $\Delta\varphi = \angle s_{A_1} - \angle s_{A_0}$. Therefore, Θ can be estimated as:

$$\Theta = \arcsin\left(\frac{\angle s_{A_1} - \angle s_{A_0}}{\pi}\right). \quad (8)$$

Note that for both array orientations in Fig. 5, Θ defines the equation of a cone, denoting the set of possible directions where the TX may be located. In the case of Fig. 5a the user can be located at $x = (\sqrt{y^2 + z^2}) \cdot \tan \Theta_h$, while in the case of fig. 5b the user can be located in $z = (\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}) \cdot \tan \Theta_v$. The TX lies in the line within the intersection of both cones.

III. Echoes indoor localization

In this section we first present an overview of Echoes (§ A), next we detail the system model for indoor positioning (§ B) and finally we present how Echoes works to accurately estimate user locations in an indoor scenario (§ C).

A. Echoes overview

Echoes employs a model-based approach for indoor localization, leveraging the combined capabilities of a small cell and a reconfigurable smart surface to estimate the position of users within a sensing area. As depicted in Fig. 6, we consider a user (TX) within the sensing area along the direction (θ_u^R, ϕ_u^R) with respect to the smart surface reference. Also, the same user is oriented horizontally with

an angle Θ_u^h and vertically with an angle Θ_u^v from the small cell receiving antenna array.

Echoes periodically probes all the configurations C_k of the smart surface's codebook using a finite set of Ψ offset values for each configuration. Since, in mobile networks, users periodically transmit reference signals in the uplink (e.g., the Uplink SRS in 5G-NR), the network constantly measures the received power per receiving antenna to estimate the quality of the channel. Echoes uses these measurements to estimate the position of a user in two steps.

- 1) In the first step, Echoes searches for the set of configurations $C^* = \{C_k^{m,*}(\psi_0^{m,*})\}$ that maximize the received power gain in each antenna m independently. Since Echoes assumes perfect knowledge of the direction of the receiver (θ_s^R, ϕ_s^R) , it uses each configuration $C_k^{m,*}(\psi_0^{m,*})$ to compute M estimations of the direction of the user $(\hat{\theta}_u^{R,m}, \hat{\phi}_u^{R,m})$ using (5) and (6). Next, Echoes averages independently the estimations for the azimuth and elevation to compute $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R)$.
- 2) In the second step, Echoes considers different pairs of antennas separated by $\frac{\lambda}{2}$ and centered to the smart surface board center. As we prove in § 2, the difference between the estimated offset values that maximize the received power gain in a pair of antennas m and m' using the optimal configuration $C_k^{m,*}$, i.e., $\hat{\psi}_0^{m,*} - \hat{\psi}_0^{m',*}$, approximate the phase difference of a signal arriving to the antenna m and m' . Echoes exploits this observation to estimate the angles $\hat{\Theta}_u^h$ and $\hat{\Theta}_u^v$ using (8) for different pairs of antennas with different orientations.

Finally, Echoes geometrically locates a user within the sensing area using the previous estimations $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R, \hat{\Theta}_u^h, \hat{\Theta}_u^v)$. It searches for the best position $(\hat{x}_u, \hat{y}_u, \hat{z}_u)$ that minimizes the sum of the mean squared error of all the angle estimations, using numerical computation of the gradient (see § C).

B. System Model

Fig. 6 depicts the indoor scenario where we have a user (TX) $u \in \mathcal{U}$ where \mathcal{U} is the set of users within the sensing area \mathcal{A} , located at the position $\mathbf{u} = (x_u, y_u, z_u)$, a small cell (RX) equipped with an array of M antennas each located at the position $\mathbf{s}_m = (x_m, y_m, z_m)$ and a smart surface located at the position $\mathbf{r} = (x_r, y_r, z_r)$. The indoor space is mostly open and has small pieces of furniture that do not block the communication signals. This space contains a squared area of size $d_s \times d_s$ where we want to sense the position of the wireless users and feed it to an upper-layer application. The small cell ensures high-quality wireless coverage, supporting high data rates and enabling accurate measurement of signal characteristics via O-RAN. The smart surface is installed in the wall opposite the small cell at the same height h , with the receiving antenna array aligned with the center of the

smart surface board. Note that as both devices are centered, the relative position of the small cell with respect to the smart surface (θ_s^R, ϕ_s^R) is $(270^\circ, 0^\circ)$. The smart surface is separated by a distance d with respect to the area's limits, to ensure its operational range limits in the azimuth.

The TX periodically sends reference signals that we denote as x using an isotropic antenna to the RX, so that it can estimate the channel (without loss of generality, we assume that x has unit power). The RX receives x from the direct path, the reflected path through the smart surface, and any other multi-path contributions. We denote the direct channel between the TX and each of the M antennas in the RX as $\mathbf{H}^d \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$. We also denote the channel between the TX and a smart surface as $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$, where N is the number of unit cells at the smart surface. Finally, we denote the channel between the smart surface and the RX as $\mathbf{H}^i \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$. We start writing the direct channel between the TX and the m -th antenna of the RX as:

$$H_m^d = \sqrt{\gamma_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m)} e^{j\psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m)} e^{j\psi_l(\mathbf{s}_m)}, \quad (9)$$

where $\gamma_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m)$ models the path loss including any multi-path effect, $\psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m)$ models the phase change due to a signal travelling a distance $\|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{s}_m\|$, and $\psi_l(\mathbf{s}_m)$ models any phase change due to multi-path. Next, we write the channel between the TX and the smart surface as:

$$\mathbf{G} = \sqrt{\gamma_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r})} e^{j\psi_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r})} \mathbf{a}_R(\theta_u^R, \phi_u^R). \quad (10)$$

\mathbf{G} is the product between the array response $\mathbf{a}_R(\theta_u^R, \phi_u^R) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ of the smart surface in the direction of the TX, $\gamma_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r})$, which models the path loss between the TX and the smart surface, and $\psi_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r})$, which models the phase change due to a signal traveling a distance $\|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{r}\|$. Next, we write the channel between the smart surface and each of the M RX antennas as

$$\mathbf{H}^i = (\Phi(\mathbf{C}_k(\psi_0))^H) \mathbf{a}_R(\theta_s^R, \phi_s^R) (\mathbf{v}^i)^H, \quad (11)$$

where Φ are the phase shifts applied by configuration $\mathbf{C}_k(\psi_0)$ as defined in § 5, $\mathbf{a}_R(\theta_s^R, \phi_s^R) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the array response of the smart surface in the direction of the small cell, and $\mathbf{v}^i \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ models the propagation between the smart surface and the M antennas of the RX array. We write each reflected path between the smart surface and the m antenna as:

$$v_m^i = \sqrt{\gamma_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m)} e^{j\psi_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m)},$$

where, as before, $\gamma_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m)$ models the path loss and $\psi_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m)$ the phase change due to a signal travelling a distance $\|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{s}_m\|$. Putting everything together, the received signal $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ in each antenna is the contribution of the direct path and the reflected path as:

$$\mathbf{y} = \underbrace{[\mathbf{H}^d]}_{\text{Direct path}} + \underbrace{(\mathbf{H}^i)^H \mathbf{G}}_{\text{Reflected path}} x + \mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ denotes the thermal noise coefficients at each RX m -th antenna whose distribution is $\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_m^2)$ and x is the transmitted signal. We can write the signal received at an antenna m as y_m , which consists of the direct path signal y_m^d , a reflected path signal y_m^i , and the noise term n . The received signal y_m can be expressed as:

$$y_m = y_m^d + y_m^i + n, \quad (13)$$

$$y_m^d = \left[\sqrt{\gamma_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m)} e^{j\psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m)} e^{j\psi_l(\mathbf{s}_m)} \right] x \quad (14)$$

$$y_m^i = \left[\sqrt{\gamma_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r})} e^{j\psi_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r})} \cdot \sqrt{\gamma_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m)} e^{j\psi_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m)} \mathbf{a}_R^H(\theta_r, \phi_r) \Phi(\mathbf{C}_k(\psi_0)) \mathbf{a}_R(\theta_t, \phi_t) \right] x. \quad (15)$$

Furthermore, as we assume that the receiving antenna array and the smart surface are centered $(\theta_s^R = 270^\circ$ and $\phi_s^R = 0)$, the reflected path signal equals to:

$$y_m^i = \left[\sqrt{\gamma_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r}) \gamma_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m)} e^{j(\psi_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r}) + \psi_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m))} \right. \quad (16)$$

$$\left. e^{j\psi_0} \left(\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{-j\psi_n} e^{j\pi n_i \cos \theta_u^R} \cdot e^{j\pi n_j \sin \phi_u^R} \right) \right] x. \quad (17)$$

Note that the signal y_m is a function of the configuration applied at the smart surface $\mathbf{C}_k(\psi_0)$ (i.e., $y_m(\mathbf{C}_k(\psi_0))$). Echoes exploits this observation to infer $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R, \hat{\Theta}_u^h, \hat{\Theta}_u^v)$ and estimate the user position.

C. Location estimation

As introduced in section § A, Echoes works in two steps. First, Echoes estimates the direction of the user $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R)$ relative to the smart surface. Second, it estimates the direction of the user relative to the small cell array $(\hat{\Theta}_u^h, \hat{\Theta}_u^v)$. Finally, Echoes combines such quantities to estimate the user position $(\hat{x}_u, \hat{y}_u, \hat{z}_u)$ using the four previous angle estimations.

1) Estimation of the user's direction relative to the smart surface

To estimate the user's direction relative to the smart surface $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R)$, Echoes searches the smart surface configurations \mathcal{C}_k , which maximize the received power gain in each of the M antennas independently. As shown in (13), the received signal is the sum of the direct path signal and the reflected path signal. Thus, y_m will be maximized if y_m^i 's amplitude is maximum, and if it is in-phase with y_m^d . On the one hand, y_m^i 's amplitude will be maximized if a configuration \mathcal{C}_k compensates the phase of the TX (θ_u^R, ϕ_u^R) as shown in (17). If \mathcal{C}_k compensates the TX direction, then:

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{-j\psi_n} e^{j\pi n_i \cos \theta_u^R} \cdot e^{j\pi n_j \sin \phi_u^R} \right| = N$$

where N is the number of unit cells. On the other hand, the configuration offset ψ_0 can be used to align the phase of y_m^i with y_m^d .

As we assume no prior knowledge of $\angle y_m^d$, Echoes periodically probes a set of different offset values for each configuration C_k of the smart surface's codebook, measuring the Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) per antenna. Using the received power measurements, Echoes infers the received power gain per configuration C_k , $|y_m(C_k(\psi_0))| - |y_m^b|$ for each m -th antenna as a function of ψ_0 where $|y_m^b|$ is the baseline received power without the smart surface.

To estimate the received power gain, Echoes starts estimating the baseline received power at the m -th antenna $|y_m^b|$, averaging S measurements of the received power with the smart surface turned off or using an absorption mode (see § IV for more details). Next, Echoes measures S samples of the received signal $|y_m(C_k(\psi_i))|$ for all offset values $\psi_i \in \Psi$ where Ψ is a finite set of possible offsets. For each offset value ψ_i , Echoes computes an estimation of the received power $|\hat{y}_m(C_k(\psi_i))|$, averaging the different S samples.

After, Echoes subtracts the baseline measurement $|\hat{y}_m^b|$ to each $|\hat{y}_m(C_k(\psi_i))|$ and fits the set of samples $\{|\hat{y}_m(C_k(\psi_1))| - |y_m^b|, |\hat{y}_m(C_k(\psi_2))| - |y_m^b|, \dots\}$ for a configuration C_k and all offsets ψ_i to a sine function of period 2π , since y_m is the result of adding two waves together. We denote the fitted function as $P_m(C_k(\Psi))$. Also, each set of samples is fitted with a dispersion of $\sigma_{P_m(C_k(\Psi))}^2$. In section § 2 we discuss the minimum number of offset values $|\Psi|$ to provide a good estimation of the received power gain. Echoes uses $\sigma_{P_m(C_k(\Psi))}^2$ and the predicted maximum of P_m to compute the best configuration $C_k^*(\Psi)$ that maximizes the received power gain in the m -th antenna as:

$$\arg \max_{C_k(\Psi)} \frac{\max(P_m(C_k(\Psi)))}{\sigma_{P_m(C_k(\Psi))}^2} \quad (18)$$

Using the set of all configuration $C_k^{m,*}(\Psi)$, Echoes estimates $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R)$, averaging the values of $(\hat{\theta}_u^{R,m}, \hat{\phi}_u^{R,m})$ that each configuration $C_k^{m,*}$ compensates.

2) Estimation of the user's angle of arrival relative to the small cell

In the second step, Echoes uses the fitted function $P_m(C_k(\Psi))$ to predict the AoA between the small cell and the user. Notice that the value ψ_0 that maximizes the function $P_m(C_k^*(\Psi))$ aligns the phase of the reflected wave with the phase of the direct wave. We denote the offset value that maximizes the received power gain in the m -th antenna as $\psi_0^{m,*}$. Thus, if the phases of y_m^d and y_m^i are aligned, we have that:

$$\angle y_m^d = \angle y_m^i$$

$$\psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m) + \psi_l(s_m) = \psi_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r}) + \psi_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m) + \psi_0^{m,*}. \quad (19)$$

The difference $\psi_0^{m,*} - \psi_0^{m',*}$ for two antennas m and m' is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_0^{m,*} - \psi_0^{m',*} = & (\psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m) - \psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_{m'})) + (\psi_l(s_m) - \psi_l(s_{m'})) \\ & + (\psi_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r}) - \psi_g(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{r})) + (\psi_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_{m'}) - \psi_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m)). \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

For a pair of antennas m and m' separated by $\frac{\lambda}{2}$ and centered with the smart surface board, we have that $\psi_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_m) = \psi_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s}_{m'})$ since $\|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{s}_m\| = \|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{s}_{m'}\|$. Thus, we can simplify $\psi_0^{m,*} - \psi_0^{m',*}$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_0^{m,*} - \psi_0^{m',*} = & (\psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m) - \psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_{m'})) + (\psi_l(s_m) - \psi_l(s_{m'})). \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

The difference between the optimal offset values $\psi_0^{m,*}$ and $\psi_0^{m',*}$ captures the phase difference $\psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_m) - \psi_d(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{s}_{m'})$ between the antennas m and m' plus the difference between the phase alteration induced by the multi-path effect. Thanks to the phase misalignment observed between the small cell antennas (caused by the variable angles Θ_u^h), we can reconstruct said angle of arrival Θ_u^h , which will be key to reconstruct the user position. In this paper, we assume that the direct path between the TX and the RX dominates any multi-path contribution as the RX is close to the TX (i.e., we assume that d_s is smaller than several tenths of meters). However, using multiple pairs of antennas oriented on the same direction (i.e., vertically or horizontally) and centered with the smart surface, it is possible to compute multiple estimations of $\psi_0^{m,*} - \psi_0^{m',*}$ and average them to reduce the effect of the multi-path. Finally, Echoes estimates the angle of arrival $\hat{\Theta}_u^h$ and $\hat{\Theta}_u^v$ for different pairs of antennas oriented vertically or horizontally using (8) and averaging the different results.

3) Echoes position estimation

On its last step, Echoes uses the previous angle estimations $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R, \hat{\Theta}_u^h, \hat{\Theta}_u^v)$ to locate a user within the sensing area solving the following optimization problem:

Problem 1 (Echoes position estimation):

$$\min_{\mathbf{u}} \|\mathbf{e}\|^2 \quad (22a)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{e} = \left(\left(\hat{\theta}_u^R - \theta_u^R \right), \left(\hat{\phi}_u^R - \phi_u^R \right), \right. \quad (22b)$$

$$\left. \left(\hat{\Theta}_u^h - \Theta_u^h \right), \left(\hat{\Theta}_u^v - \Theta_u^v \right) \right)$$

$$\theta_u^R = \text{atan2}((y_u - y_r), (x_u - x_r)) - \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (22c)$$

$$\phi_u^R = \arcsin\left(\frac{z_u - z_r}{\|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{r}\|}\right) \quad (22d)$$

$$\Theta_u^v = \arctan\left(\frac{z_u - z_m}{\sqrt{(x_u - x_m)^2 + (y_u - y_m)^2}}\right) \quad (22e)$$

$$\Theta_u^h = \arctan\left(\frac{x_u - x_m}{\sqrt{(z_u - z_m)^2 + (y_u - y_m)^2}}\right) \quad (22f)$$

$$\text{s. t. } \mathbf{u} = (x_u, y_u, z_u) \in \mathcal{A}, \quad (22g)$$

where, $\hat{\theta}_u^R$, $\hat{\phi}_u^R$, $\hat{\Theta}_u^v$, $\hat{\Theta}_u^h$ are the expected measurements for the variables θ_u^R , ϕ_u^R , Θ_u^v , Θ_u^h for a user in position \mathbf{u} . Specifically, equations (22e) and (22f) solve the cone equations for AoA estimation in the small cell as described in Section II.D and represented in Fig. 5. The function $\text{atan2}(y, x)$ is defined as:

$$\text{atan2}(y, x) = \begin{cases} \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) & \text{if } x > 0, \\ \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) + \pi & \text{if } x < 0 \text{ and } y \geq 0, \\ \arctan\left(\frac{y}{x}\right) - \pi & \text{if } x < 0 \text{ and } y < 0, \\ \pi/2 & \text{if } x = 0 \text{ and } y > 0, \\ -\pi/2 & \text{if } x = 0 \text{ and } y < 0, \\ \text{undefined} & \text{if } x = y = 0. \end{cases}$$

Since the space of solutions for Problem 1 lies in the Euclidean space and $\|\mathbf{e}\|^2$ is continuous and convex in the sensing area \mathcal{A} , it can be solved using numerical methods [35]. Furthermore, if we discretize the positions within the sensing area \mathcal{A} into a finite set, we can solve Problem 1 by computing $\|\mathbf{e}\|^2$ for all possible positions. Algorithm 1 summarizes the different steps that Echoes follows to estimate the position \mathbf{u} of a user.

Algorithm 1 consists of two main parts. First, the algorithm scans all the configurations of the smart surface and corresponding phase offsets. Second, it computes the phase differences across the antennas using the data collected during this scan. In practice, the first stage dominates the overall runtime, as the measurements require a minimum duration to be performed, regardless of the available computational power. The complexity of this initial sensing stage scales as $O(|\mathcal{C}||\Psi|)$, where $|\mathcal{C}|$ is the number of codebook configurations and $|\Psi|$, is the number of phase offsets being probed. Importantly, this stage is independent of the number of users in the cell.

Algorithm 1 Echoes

```

1: Input:
   •  $\mathcal{C}, \Psi, \mathcal{U}$ 
2: Output: For each user  $u \in \mathcal{U}$ 
   •  $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R), (\hat{\Theta}_u^h, \hat{\Theta}_u^v), \mathbf{u}$ 
   /* 1 - Perform all the necessary measurements */
3: Measure  $\mathcal{Y}_m^b = \{|y_m^b|_0, |y_m^b|_1, \dots, |y_m^b|_{S-1}\}, \forall u_i \in \mathcal{U}, \forall m$ 
4:  $|\hat{y}_m^b| \leftarrow \overline{\mathcal{Y}_m^b}, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall m$ 
5: for  $\forall \mathcal{C}_k \in \mathcal{C}$  do
6:   for  $\forall \psi_i \in \Psi$  do
7:     Configure the smart surface with  $\mathcal{C}_k(\psi_i)$ .
8:     Measure  $\mathcal{Y}_m^{\mathcal{C}_k(\psi_i)} = \{|y_m(\mathcal{C}_k(\psi_i))|_0, |y_m(\mathcal{C}_k(\psi_i))|_1, \dots, |y_m(\mathcal{C}_k(\psi_i))|_{S-1}\} \forall u_i \in \mathcal{U}, \forall m$ 
9:      $|\hat{y}_m(\mathcal{C}_k(\psi_i))| \leftarrow \overline{\mathcal{Y}_m^{\mathcal{C}_k(\psi_i)}}, \forall u_i \in \mathcal{U}, \forall m$ 
10:   end for
11: end for
12: Compute  $P_m(\mathcal{C}_k(\Psi)), \forall u \in \mathcal{U}$  and  $\forall m$ 
13: for  $\forall u \in \mathcal{U}$  do
14:   /* 2 - Compute  $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R)$  */
15:    $\mathcal{C}_k^{m,*} \leftarrow \arg \max_{\mathcal{C}_k(\Psi)} \frac{\max(P_m(\mathcal{C}_k(\Psi)))}{\sigma_{P_m(\mathcal{C}_k(\Psi))}^2}$ 
16:   Compute  $(\hat{\theta}_u^{R,m}, \hat{\phi}_u^{R,m})$  using  $\mathcal{C}_k^{m,*}$ , (5) and (6)
17:    $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R) \leftarrow \{(\hat{\theta}_u^{R,0}, \hat{\phi}_u^{R,0}), \dots, (\hat{\theta}_u^{R,M-1}, \hat{\phi}_u^{R,M-1})\}$ 
18:   /* 3 - Compute  $(\hat{\Theta}_u^h, \hat{\Theta}_u^v)$  */
19:   for each pair of  $p_i$  antennas  $m$  and  $m'$  separated  $\frac{\lambda}{2}$  and centered with the smart surface do
20:      $\psi_0^{m,*} \leftarrow \arg \max_{\psi_0} P_m(\mathcal{C}_k(\Psi))$ 
21:      $\psi_0^{m',*} \leftarrow \arg \max_{\psi_0} P_{m'}(\mathcal{C}_k(\Psi))$ 
22:     if  $m$  and  $m'$  are horizontally aligned then
23:        $\hat{\Theta}_u^{h,p_i} \leftarrow \arcsin\left(\frac{\psi_0^{m',*} - \psi_0^{m,*}}{\pi}\right)$ 
24:     else
25:        $\hat{\Theta}_u^{v,p_i} \leftarrow \arcsin\left(\frac{\psi_0^{m',*} - \psi_0^{m,*}}{\pi}\right)$ 
26:     end if
27:   end for
28:    $\hat{\Theta}_u^h = \{\hat{\Theta}_u^{h,p_i}\}$ 
29:    $\hat{\Theta}_u^v = \{\hat{\Theta}_u^{v,p_i}\}$ 
30:    $\mathbf{u} \leftarrow$  solve PROBLEM 1 using  $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R, \hat{\Theta}_u^h, \hat{\Theta}_u^v)$ 
31: end for
32:  $\forall u \in \mathcal{U}$  return  $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\phi}_u^R), (\hat{\Theta}_u^h, \hat{\Theta}_u^v), \mathbf{u} = (x_u, y_u, z_u)$ 

```

While Echoes reliance on precomputed codebooks introduces a dependence in the system, and the granularity of the codebook impacts its accuracy capabilities, we believe that the maturity of the smart surface optimal configuration problem is enough for these issues not to present an accuracy issue regarding scalability. Note that Algorithm 1 has \mathcal{C} and Ψ as input parameters, effectively generalizing the approach to any smart surface hardware.

FIGURE 7: Echoes' O-RAN architecture integration.

IV. Running Echoes

This section starts describing the system design of Echoes (§ A) and later presents the Echoes' experimental platform (§ B) and validation (§ C).

A. System design

1) O-RAN architecture integration

As described in § III, our indoor scenario consists of an O-RAN small cell covering the desired sensing area and a reconfigurable smart surface that enables us to estimate the users' positions. The smart surface is connected to the edge O-Cloud platform via a wired connection, such as an Ethernet or USB cable. The DU hosts a dApp [32] that enables the reconfiguration of the smart surface according to a predefined codebook. Echoes is deployed as an xApp in the near-RT RIC of the O-RAN architecture (see Fig. 3). The xApp performs the following functions: (i) receiving Uplink Sounding Reference Signal Received Power (UL SRS RP) measurements from each small cell antenna via the E2 interface, (ii) reconfiguring the smart surface using the corresponding Echoes dApp, and (iii) estimating user positions once Echoes has collected all the necessary measurements. Fig. 7 shows the components of our system.

Overall, the described Echoes architecture is fully defined within the O-RAN specifications, facilitating integration and deployment of the Echoes solution to any O-RAN compliant cell by avoiding heavy modifications of vendor-specific gNB software.

2) Workflow

Fig. 8 depicts Echoes operational workflow, which consists of the following four steps: (1) *calling the Echoes* in which the xApp receives a location subscription request, (2) *listening to the Echoes* in which the xApp subscribes to the power measurements of the uplink reference signal periodically sent from a user of the small cell, (3) *tuning the Echoes* in which the xApp reconfigures the smart surface via the dApp, and (4) *grasping the Echoes* in which the xApp runs algorithm 1 to locate a user. In the following, we detail each step:

- 1) *Calling the Echoes*: Echoes' workflow starts when the xApp receives a location subscription request from the application whose objective is to locate a user within the sensing area. The application sends a positioning service request using the A1 interface;
- 2) *Listening to the Echoes*: Echoes's xApp subscribes to the periodic power level measurements of the Uplink Sounding Reference Signal (UL SRS) per receiving antenna measured from the target user equipment (UE). Echoes uses the E2 interface to request the small cell the periodic metric reports. Conveniently, this measurement is widely supported by many of the gNB vendors, which is available through the E2SM-KPM in O-RAN [30];
- 3) *Tuning the Echoes*: Echoes' core algorithm for location estimation is based on iteratively reconfiguring a smart surface according to algorithm 1 and compiling all the necessary power measurements to infer the position of a user within a sensing area. To reconfigure the smart surface, Echoes' xApp uses the proxy-like Echoes dApp co-located with the small cell. The dApp locally controls the smart surface at the site, reconfiguring all its elements through the F1-x interface [36]. Echoes sends to the dApp the index k of a codebook configuration C_k and an offset value ψ_0 to be applied. The interface between Echoes's xApp and the dApp uses the E2 interface, leveraging the E2AP and E2SM sets of predefined procedures and services that enable the control communication. The dApp expands E2SM, enabling two smart surface-specific report and control functions: (i) setting a codebook configuration in the smart surface and (ii) reporting all the supported codebook configurations and the current codebook setting configured in the smart surface;
- 4) *Grasping the Echoes*: Once Echoes has received all the necessary power level measurements, Echoes estimates the position of a user according to § 3. Echoes procedure runs periodically to progressively improve the sensed positions. Echoes' xApp periodically sends the obtained position estimations to the subscribed application.

B. Experimental platform

In order to evaluate Echoes, we have set up an experimental testbed. Fig. 9a depicts our indoors testbed conceptually, and Fig. 9b shows a real picture of it. Our testbed consists of one transmitter (TX), one receiver (RX), an O-cloud edge server, and a planar smart surface prototype. We map the TX to a UE and the RX to the small cell of our scenario. While we do assume and ensure Line-of-Sight (LoS) between a user in the sensing area and the small cell, the environment where we operate is a real-life office without any adaptation, elimination of multipath, addition of anechoic surfaces, etc. This scatter-rich environment has been one of the greatest

FIGURE 8: Echoes' workflow.

FIGURE 10: NEC Smart surface board.

(a) Conceptual design of our testbed.

(b) Real testbed.

FIGURE 9: Echoes testbed.

challenges in the experimental section of our work, and it intends to serve as technological benchmarking in a relevant environment, beyond laboratory validation. This is both true for our proposal and the smart surface prototype employed.

We implemented the transmitter and receiver using two USRPs B210 running srsRAN [37]. The TX communication stack runs in a desktop PC, and the RX's DU and CU run in the edge server that serves as the O-Cloud platform. Both RF front-ends work at 5.3 GHz with a wavelength of $\lambda = 5.65$ cm. The RX has two omnidirectional low-gain antennas separated by $\frac{\lambda}{2}$, while the TX is equipped with two highly directional horn antennas. We opted to use horn antennas for evaluating Echoes as they reduce the number of scatterers present in our testbed and provide experimental repeatability.

The server running the O-Cloud also runs the O-RAN SC Near-RT RIC (i-release) [38], where we deploy Echoes as an xApp. Echoes can collect the uplink power measurement reports per antenna provided by the RX. The edge server also has a smart surface connected via a USB interface working as F1-x interface, as explained in § A, and contains the smart surface dApp, which exposes the available codebooks and allows for controlling the smart surface.

The smart surface is conveniently placed close to the front wall. In this way, the smart surface is able to cover as much space as possible for estimating the position of different

(a) Codebook configuration with $\theta = 30^\circ, \phi = 0^\circ$ and $\psi_0 = 0^\circ$ (b) Codebook configuration with $\theta = 30^\circ, \phi = 0^\circ$ and $\psi_0 = 51.42^\circ$

FIGURE 11: $(30^\circ, 0^\circ)$ configuration with different offsets.

users. We place the small cell receiver at the other end of our room, centering it with the smart surface and providing good coverage to all the users. Next, we set up the TX between the smart surface and the RX. Notice that for our setup, it is possible to move the TX and take different measurements. Finally, in our setup, we have placed the TX, the RX, and the smart surface in the same plane. This allows us to be able to estimate the position only using two horizontally placed antennas. Notice that we only probe configurations for the different values of the azimuth θ , as having the TX and RX in the same plane sets the optimal elevation to $\phi = 0^\circ$. Echoes estimates the position using $(\hat{\theta}_u^R, \hat{\Theta}_u^h)$.

1) Smart surface board

The prototype smart surface board of our testbed has 10×10 unit cells implemented using patch antennas, and operates in the 5.3 GHz band, as characterized in [26]. The patch antennas are separated by $\delta = \frac{\lambda}{2} = 2.82$ cm. Fig. 10 shows a picture of the smart surface board. Each unit cell element is configurable with a 3-bits phase shift. The combination 000 turns off an individual element while the other 7 possible bit combinations induce a phase shift $\psi_n = \frac{2\pi}{7}n \forall n \in \{0, \dots, 6\}$, which correspond to the phase shifts in degrees of $\psi_n \in \{0^\circ, 51.42^\circ, 102.85^\circ, 154.28^\circ, 205.71^\circ, 257.14^\circ, 308.57^\circ\}$, respectively. Turning all elements off sets the smart surface into the *absorption mode*. Our smart surface achieves an HPBW equal to $\approx 10^\circ$ degrees when reflecting a signal towards a specific direction.

(a) Codebook configurations with no phase shift offset. (b) Codebook configurations with best phase shift offset.

FIGURE 12: Received power gains

To navigate all possible configurations, we employ a far-field pre-computed codebook. As each smart surface’s patch antenna only supports 7 phase shift values, codebook configurations are discretized by rounding the phase shift value of each element to the nearest possible value ψ_n . When applying a phase shift offset value to all elements, we always add a value that is a multiple of the possible phase shift values for $n \in \{0, \dots, 6\}$. The codebook azimuth and elevation angles range from $[-60^\circ, 60^\circ]$ and $[-45^\circ, 45^\circ]$, respectively, in steps of 5° degrees up to a total of 437 configurations. Fig. 11a shows a smart surface codebook configuration with $\theta = 30^\circ$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$ and no offset value. On the other hand, Fig. 11b shows the same codebook configuration when we apply an offset value of $\psi_0 = 51.42^\circ$.

C. Experimental validation

Before presenting the experimental evaluation of Echoes in § V, we present an experimental validation of our testbed showing the effect on the received power gain of different smart surface’s codebook configurations (§ 1) and adding different phase shift offset values (§ 2).

1) Smart surface configuration gain

To evaluate the received power gain when using the smart surface, we started probing all codebook configurations along the azimuth axis in the range $\theta \in [-55^\circ, 55^\circ]$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$. Fig. 12a depicts the received power gain as the measured power difference between setting a codebook configuration in the smart surface and setting all elements to absorption mode (i.e., the baseline received power). As we can see, the received power gains are between 0.2 and -2 dB for our testbed. Notice that the measured power gain is non-zero across all azimuth directions, indicating the presence of scattering and reflections, and confirms that the environment is non-ideal as we summarized above in § B. Also, we observe a clear direction for decreasing the received gain, which is using configurations with an azimuth value of $\theta = 20^\circ$. In this environment, the received signal does not only come from the smart surface’s reflected signals, but also from other paths between the TX and the RX, which can combine constructively or destructively. Thus, aligning the phase of the reflected path signal is key to noticing positive power gain changes.

(a) Average received power for all codebook configurations. (b) Received power gain per antenna using the best phase shift offset value.

FIGURE 13: Received power gain as a function of the phase shift offset.

FIGURE 14: Number of samples required to fit the received power gain.

2) Smart surface phase shift offset alignment gain

To evaluate the effect of adding a phase shift offset to all elements, we probe again the same set of configurations by adding to each one of them all of the 7 possible phase shift offset values, as detailed in § 1. After probing them all, we select the configuration with a phase shift offset value that provided the best received power gain in dB, as shown in Fig. 12b. We see again a received power gain peak around $\theta = 20^\circ$, but this time with a positive received power gain. Now, the optimal reflection is almost in-phase with the direct path signal.

To complete the analysis, Fig. 13a depicts the received power gain as a function of the phase shift applied. To create this figure, we have centered the highest gain offset value for each codebook configuration at 0° . Note that for a configuration $\mathcal{C}_k(\psi_{best})$, where ψ_{best} is the phase offset yielding the highest gain, we center that configuration at $\psi_{best} = 0^\circ$, and all other possible phase offset configurations with offset ψ_i become $\mathcal{C}_k(\psi_{best} + \psi_i)$. The effect of adding an offset value creates a sinusoidal pattern on the received power gain. This shows empirically the reason why we fit the offset results to a sine function, as described in § C. For the best smart surface configuration, Fig. 13b shows the normalized received power gain measured for the two antennas available in the testbed. We can clearly see the sinusoidal pattern that different offsets create on the received gain. Also, notice that both sine functions are not in-phase, and precisely that observation is what allows us to measure the angle of arrival between a user and the receiver.

FIGURE 15: Predicted UE positions in 2D space.

(a) Smart surface steering angle θ_u^R . (b) Horizontal angle of arrival Θ_u^h .

FIGURE 16: CDFs of Echoes angle predictions.

Finally, we demonstrate that the number of measurements required to accurately predict the absolute phase at each antenna can be reduced with only a small trade-off in accuracy. Fig. 14 illustrates the phase error for different numbers of offset measurements (i.e., 2, 3, 5) as a function of the gain introduced by a smart surface configuration to the direct link. As shown, higher gains lead to more accurate power predictions, as the reflected signal aligns correctly with the RX target. This, in turn, results in a cleaner interference pattern that better conforms to the sinusoidal model.

V. Echoes experimental evaluation

A. Experimental results

To evaluate Echoes, we position the TX at several locations and evaluate the different Echoes’s estimated UE locations. Fig. 15a depicts the different considered UE positions by black dots. These positions span the ranges $\theta_u^R \in [215^\circ, 245^\circ]$ and $\Theta_u^h \in [27^\circ, 73^\circ]$ and cover distances between 1.3 m and 4.3 m to the smart surface. As all the elements are located within the same plane, we restrict the codebook probing step of Echoes to configurations \mathcal{C}_k where $\theta \in [-55^\circ, 55^\circ]$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$.

Fig. 15a also depicts in red crosses the predicted positions of Echoes for each tested UE location. Overall, the pro-

FIGURE 17: CDFs of the positioning error on the x-axis, y-axis, and the total distance d .

jections remain well-aligned along the TX-to-smart surface direction, providing an accurate θ_u^R prediction. Conversely, some fuzziness occurs along the TX-to-small-cell direction due to less accurate Θ_u^h estimations. In particular, the derived positions tend to shift in the southerly direction except for two outliers. Fig. 16a evaluates the prediction error of θ_u^R via its cumulative distribution function (CDF). The results show that the mean absolute error (MAE) for θ_u^R is 2.15° , and the 90th percentile error is 5° . Therefore, we conclude that the codebook’s steering angle discretization of 5° ultimately limits the accuracy of estimating θ_u^R . On the other hand, fig. 16b, plots the prediction error of Θ_u^h showing a MAE of 14.15° and an error of 30° at the 90th percentile. Since we are only using one pair of antennas, the error is quite high and limits our ability to locate the TX in the different tested positions. Using additional pairs of antennas would help us reduce this error. Finally, Fig. 17a quantifies the total position error along the x axis, the y axis and the combined error d (i.e., $d = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$), revealing larger discrepancies in the y -direction, which strongly correlates with the prediction error of Θ_u^h . The distance error exhibits a MAE of 0.92 m and a 90th percentile error of 2.1 m.

B. Simulation benchmark

To benchmark Echoes, we simulate our experimental setup to obtain localization results under a traditional AoA-based system, as the one used in [45]. The simulation benchmark system considers a pair of beamforming-capable devices (such as smart surfaces or small cells) and locates users within the intersection of the orientation of the selected beams in the different devices. In this beam-training based localization method, the localization is completed thanks to the double AoA information source, while in our case we exploit the phase shift in the receiving antennas, as shown in Fig. 13. We assume that the HPBW in the horizontal direction for the different devices is equal to $0.886 \frac{\lambda}{N_i \delta \cos \theta_u^R}$ [46], [47] where N_i is the number of elements in the array, λ is the wavelength, δ is the inter-element distance between array elements and θ_u^R is the direction of the user with respect to the normal direction of the array. Fig. 15b shows the results of a single simulation round compared to the ground truth values. We observe a similar level of scattering with a comparable error distribution as Fig. 15a using Echoes. To assess Echoes’ performance gain compared to the bench-

	Paper	Target Scenario	Cal.	Pre-requisites	Pos. Target	Solution Approach	Evaluation	Error (m)	Tech. integration
Smart Surface-Aided Positioning	[5]	Indoors/WiFi	①	②, ③, ④, ⑤.	Passive target	Beam training to optimally combine the reflected signals at a receiver.	Experimental, tested in a real environment.	0.15	No
	[39]	Indoors/WiFi	①	②, ③, ④, ⑤.	Passive target	Joint beamforming and smart surface reflection optimization.	Simulations	0.1	No
	[40]	Indoors/WiFi	-	②, ④	Active RX target	Beam training on two smart surfaces to optimize the received power at the user side to estimate the location.	Experimental, tested in a real environment.	0.5	Integrated with WiFi
	Echoes	Indoors/5G	-	③, ④.	Active 5G TX target	Combining beam training at the smart surface with angle of arrival estimation at the small cell via the reflective surface.	Experimental, tested in a real environment	0.9	Yes, integrated with 5G/O-RAN
Other Positioning Technologies	UWB [41] [42] [43]	Indoors / Specialised hardware deployment	-	⑥	Active target	Target localization using a mixture of techniques such as ToF, TWR, AoA and TDoA estimations	Experimental	0.05	Yes, integrated mostly with WiFi
	Deep learning fingerprinting [1] [44]	Indoors/WiFi	①	③	Active WiFi user	Position estimation using deep learning models trained on RSSI, , or other features from multiple AP locations	Experimental and simulations	0.2 – 1.0 (depending on environment and model)	Yes, integrated mostly with WiFi

Legend: ①: Environment calibration required; ②: TX position must be known; ③: RX position must be known; ④: Smart surface position must be known; ⑤: Dedicated receiver required; ⑥: UWB transceivers (anchors and tags) spread across the sensing area.

TABLE 1: State-of-the-art comparison table for smart surface-aided positioning systems.

mark, Fig. 17b shows the cumulative density function of the error in the x-axis, y-axis, and the total distance d for 10^5 rounds, totalling $1.3 \cdot 10^6$ simulated positions. Both Echoes and the simulation obtain similar error results, with Echoes improving the localization error slightly compared to the simulation benchmark. The 25th, 50th, 75th error percentiles are 0.61, 1.17, 2.01 m for the simulation benchmark while Echoes achieves 0.44, 0.66, 1.06 m error percentiles.

C. Analytical benchmark

Lastly, we present an analytical benchmark in Table 1 to compare Echoes with other state-of-the-art approaches. Table 1 includes two categories of solutions. First, we compare Echoes with other localization systems that utilize smart surfaces to estimate the user’s position, grouped under the “Smart Surface-Aided Positioning” rows. Second, we include other positioning technologies, such as Ultra Wide Band Techniques (UWB) and deep learning-based fingerprinting, which do not use smart surfaces; these are grouped under “Other Positioning Technologies.”

Within the first group, we analytically compare Echoes with the methods described in [5], [39], and [40]. The

first two works follow similar methodologies but employ different techniques to localize passive targets within a sensing area. Both argue that a dedicated receiver placed at the edge of the sensing area receives a reflected signal from the sensing target composed of the reflection solely at the target (i.e. the TX–Target–RX path), the reflection at the smart surface and the target (i.e. the TX–SS–Target–RX path) and other multipath contributions. In [5], the authors calibrate the environment and develop a method that scans the sensing area, mapping optimal reflections on the smart surface to effectively combine the TX–Target–RX and TX–SS–Target–RX paths toward the target location. In [39], the authors propose a joint beamforming and smart surface reflection optimization approach to locate a person within the sensing area. In contrast, [40] leverages RIS to perform WiFi beam scanning, enabling clients to determine their direction using a single scan. This approach fully utilizes RIS reconfigurability to create distinguishable beam features, allowing the system to extract stable and accurate direction information even in complex and dynamic environments.

On the other hand, Echoes solution does not need to undergo an environment calibration as [5], [39]. However,

as previous solutions, including [40], it requires a priori knowledge of the positions of the smart surface(s) and any transmitters or receivers used to sense any target. *Echoes* combines a beam training phase at the smart surface with an offset measurement phase to estimate the angle of arrival at a small cell. Additionally, *Echoes* is fully integrated within the JCAS paradigm by performing sensing without any interruption on the communication channels, while solutions like [40] necessitate dedicated broadcasting procedures. Similarly to the previous solutions, *Echoes* has been tested in a real indoor environment.

In contrast to smart surface-aided techniques, the “Other Positioning Technologies” group includes methods such as UWB-based localization [41]–[43] and deep learning-based fingerprinting [1], [44]. UWB techniques rely on specialized hardware deployments and actively track targets using a combination of ToF, TWR, AoA, and TDoA estimations. These methods are highly accurate, achieving localization errors as low as 0.05 meters in experimental settings, but require dedicated infrastructure and hardware integration, typically alongside WiFi. Deep learning fingerprinting, on the other hand, estimates user position by training models on features like RSSI across multiple access points. While this approach can be deployed in WiFi-enabled indoor environments without specialized hardware, its accuracy varies significantly—ranging from 0.2 to 1.0 meters—depending on the environment and model used. Despite these differences, both methods are predominantly integrated with WiFi networks and rely on active user participation.

VI. Related Work

Smart surface-aided Localization: A number of works have studied the effects of smart surfaces on positioning systems [48]–[51]. *Echoes* focuses on the MISO 1 Smart Surface 1 BS setting as described in [52]. According to [17], localization of a single-antenna UE through the signals received from reflections from a single RIS to the UE is not feasible in the far-field when the RIS reflection coefficients remain constant across all OFDM symbols. In this sense, *Echoes* uses 2 RX antennas at the BS to localize the UE, considering far-field. Other works related to *Echoes* are [53], which also uses received signal strength for multi-user localization using a probabilistic approach, and [54], which studies the effect of phase shift offsets in UE localization. Also, there are a number of works that use smart surfaces for localization using the MUSIC algorithm to resolve the AoA [21], [24], [55], [56]. However, as mentioned in Section V.C, only a few experimental works follow the approach of phase-shift tuning for passive indoor localization as *Echoes* does, such as [5], [39]. Other experimental works use generic RF signals, such as [45], another type of fingerprinting-based localization system with comparable positioning accuracy, where smart surface configurations can be mapped to specific locations using Deep Learning, and [57], [58], which use UWB signals to achieve centimetre-level accuracy. These

works, however, are based on a radar-like approach and are not suitable as JCAS systems.

Joint Communication and Sensing: A huge amount of work has been done on RF-based positioning. Traditionally, most relevant localization approaches are based on radar sensing [28], [59], [60], fingerprinting [61], [62], multi-lateralization/ multi-angulation [29], [63], [64] or AoA plus time of flight [65], [66]. JCAS proposes combining such positioning systems with existing communication technologies, e.g., using 5G-NR or WiFi signals. Reference JCAS works on passive indoor localization are [67], [68], which report accuracies lower than 1m. Regarding 5G, 3GPP standards include mmWave location sensing [69]. However, sub-6 GHz JCAS systems hold the advantage of being based on the existing widely-deployed 5G infrastructure [63], [64], [70]. *Echoes* falls within this category, using existing 5G NR signals on the 5.3 GHz band.

Integration of Smart Surfaces and JCAS in Open RAN:

The O-RAN ecosystem offers new opportunities to integrate RIS and JCAS systems into cellular networking [71]–[74]. However, many of the JCAS technologies require low-level I/Q samples processing, making them difficult to integrate into O-RAN’s RIC. In this sense, *Echoes* is in line with O-RAN by being deployed as an xApp in the near-RT RIC and only requires metrics that are already available in the E2 interface. Additionally, *Echoes* uses a *dApp* [32] to control the smart surface at the site, which is in line with current efforts to adopt them as JCAS enablers [33]. Similarly, efforts are being made to integrate smart surfaces into O-RAN [36], [75]. These works propose to use RIS-specific interfaces at different time scales, such as the F1-x used by *Echoes*, to enable fast re-configurations and joint BS and smart surfaces beamforming in a millisecond time frame [76]. On the other hand, works such as [77], [78] aim for self-configuring smart surfaces without even a control channel.

VII. Future work

While this work demonstrates the feasibility of the proposed *Echoes* approach using precomputed codebooks and a single smart surface, several avenues remain open for future exploration. First, although our current implementation probes all beam configurations sequentially, this approach may become inefficient in large-scale scenarios. To address this limitation, we plan to investigate methods for accelerating the beam training phase. We plan to exploit the ability of the receiver to measure power at each antenna element independently, which would allow simultaneous probing of multiple beam directions. This could significantly reduce the time required for the initial sensing stage. Second, as the size of the sensing area increases, maintaining fine spatial resolution will require proportionally larger codebooks. In such cases, using multiple coordinated smart surfaces could provide broader coverage and improved granularity without overloading any single device. Exploring multi-

surface coordination strategies and their impact on localization performance will be a key focus of our future work. Finally, extending our framework to intelligent omni-surfaces (IOS) [79] introduces new challenges and opportunities. Supporting users on both sides of a surface will require dual-sector codebooks and possibly adaptive scheduling to manage the increased configuration complexity. Future work will investigate tailored strategies for IOS-enabled localization and assess their performance trade-offs.

VIII. Conclusions

In this paper, we have pioneered Echoes, an indoor localization system, which leverages the available metrics of an O-RAN small cell and smart surface to predict user's positions within a sensing area. Echoes relies on the periodic uplink reference signals and the available power level measurements in O-RAN to locate a user by suitably reconfiguring the smart surface.

Echoes reconfigures the smart surface with different phase offset values and extracts the direction of the user that maximizes the gain at the receiver, as well as the Angle-of-Arrival (AoA) between the user and the small cell. We have studied the performance of Echoes in a realistic 5G indoor environment, providing insights on practical issues of uncontrolled, rich scattering environments. Moreover, we have presented Echoes's system integration and demonstrated its feasibility within the O-RAN architecture. Our results have shown a localization accuracy in the sub-meter range (MAE = 0.9m). Finally, we have compared Echoes to a simulation benchmark system, which locates users using the beam orientation of different beam forming devices. Echoes improves the localization error without requiring beamforming capabilities, achieving a 50th percentile of 0.66 m of the location error while the simulation benchmark achieves a 50th percentile location error of 1.17m.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Ayyalasomayajula, A. Arun, C. Wu, S. Sharma, A. R. Sethi, D. Vasisht, and D. Bharadia, "Deep learning based wireless localization for indoor navigation," in *Proceedings of the 26th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking*, 2020, pp. 1–14.
- [2] H. Zhang, H. Zhang, B. Di, K. Bian, Z. Han, and L. Song, "Metalocalization: Reconfigurable intelligent surface aided multi-user wireless indoor localization," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 20, no. 12, pp. 7743–7757, 2021.
- [3] E. Soltanaghaei, A. Kalyanaraman, and K. Whitehouse, "Multipath triangulation: Decimeter-level wifi localization and orientation with a single unaided receiver," in *Proceedings of the 16th annual international conference on mobile systems, applications, and services*, 2018, pp. 376–388.
- [4] J. Wang, H. Jiang, J. Xiong, K. Jamieson, X. Chen, D. Fang, and B. Xie, "Lifs: Low human-effort, device-free localization with fine-grained subcarrier information," in *Proceedings of the 22nd Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking*, 2016, pp. 243–256.
- [5] G. Zhang, D. Zhang, H. Deng, Y. Wu, F. Zhan, and Y. Chen, "Practical passive indoor localization with intelligent reflecting surface," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, 2024.
- [6] B. Wang, S. Li, G. Battistelli, and L. Chisci, "Fast iterative adaptive approach for indoor localization with distributed 5g small cells," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 1980–1984, 2022.
- [7] M. Gucciardo, I. Tinnirello, G. M. Dell'Aera, and M. Caretti, "A flexible 4g/5g control platform for fingerprint-based indoor localization," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2019-IEEE conference on computer communications workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPs)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 744–749.
- [8] X. Zhou, L. Chen, Y. Ruan, and R. Chen, "Indoor localization with multi-beam of 5g new radio signals," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 2024.
- [9] Y. Ruan, L. Chen, X. Zhou, G. Guo, and R. Chen, "Hi-loc: Hybrid indoor localization via enhanced 5g nr csi," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 71, pp. 1–15, 2022.
- [10] Z. Wang, Z. Liu, Y. Shen, A. Conti, and M. Z. Win, "Location awareness in beyond 5g networks via reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 2011–2025, 2022.
- [11] M. Lin, M. Xu, X. Wan, H. Liu, Z. Wu, J. Liu, B. Deng, D. Guan, and S. Zha, "Single sensor to estimate doa with programmable metasurface," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 12, pp. 10 187–10 197, 2021.
- [12] A. Albanese, G. Encinas-Lago, V. Sciancalepore, X. Costa-Pérez, D.-T. Phan-Huy, and S. Ros, "Ris-aware indoor network planning: The rennes railway station case," in *ICC 2022 - IEEE International Conference on Communications*, 2022, pp. 2028–2034.
- [13] G. Encinas-Lago, A. Albanese, V. Sciancalepore, X. Costa-Pérez, A. Banchs, and D.-T. Phan-Huy, "A cost-effective riss deployment to abate the coverage problem in b5g networks," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 15 276–15 290, 2024.
- [14] G. Encinas-Lago, A. Albanese, V. Sciancalepore, M. Di Renzo, and X. Costa-Pérez, "Unlocking metasurface practicality for b5g networks: Ai-assisted ris planning," in *GLOBECOM 2023 - 2023 IEEE Global Communications Conference*, 2023, pp. 6560–6566.
- [15] S. Zeng, H. Zhang, B. Di, Z. Han, and L. Song, "Reconfigurable intelligent surface (ris) assisted wireless coverage extension: Ris orientation and location optimization," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 269–273, 2021.
- [16] G. Encinas-Lago, V. Sciancalepore, H. Wymeersch, M. D. Renzo, and X. Costa-Pérez, "Riloco: An isac-oriented ai solution to build ris-empowered networks," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, pp. 1–1, 2025.
- [17] D.-R. Emenonye, H. S. Dhillon, and R. M. Buehrer, "Fundamentals of ris-aided localization in the far-field," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 3408–3424, 2024.
- [18] R. Ghazalian, G. C. Alexandropoulos, G. Seco-Granados, H. Wymeersch, and R. Jantti, "Joint 3d user and 6d hybrid reconfigurable intelligent surface localization," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 2024.
- [19] M. Hua, Q. Wu, W. Chen, Z. Fei, H. C. So, and C. Yuen, "Intelligent reflecting surface-assisted localization: Performance analysis and algorithm design," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 84–88, 2023.
- [20] J. Zhang, J. Wu, and R. Wang, "User localization and environment mapping with the assistance of ris," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 73, no. 6, pp. 8549–8562, 2024.
- [21] J. He, A. Fakhreddine, C. Vanwynsberghe, H. Wymeersch, and G. C. Alexandropoulos, "3d localization with a single partially-connected receiving ris: Positioning error analysis and algorithmic design," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 72, no. 10, pp. 13 190–13 202, 2023.
- [22] H. Wymeersch, J. He, B. Denis, A. Clemente, and M. Juntti, "Radio localization and mapping with reconfigurable intelligent surfaces: Challenges, opportunities, and research directions," *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 52–61, 2020.
- [23] A. M. Nor, O. Fratu, and S. Halunga, "Positioning information-based codebook for reconfigurable intelligent surface passive beamforming," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 4, pp. 3115–3130, 2023.
- [24] M. Hua, G. Chen, K. Meng, S. Ma, C. Yuen, and H. C. So, "3d multi-target localization via intelligent reflecting surface: Protocol and analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 2024.
- [25] S. Lv, Y. Liu, X. Xu, A. Nallanathan, and A. L. Swindlehurst, "Ris-aided near-field mimo communications: Codebook and beam training design," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 2024.
- [26] M. Rossanese, P. Mursia, A. Garcia-Saavedra, V. Sciancalepore, A. Asadi, and X. Costa-Perez, "Designing, building, and characterizing rf switch-based reconfigurable intelligent surfaces," in *Proceedings of*

- the 16th ACM Workshop on Wireless Network Testbeds, Experimental evaluation & Characterization, 2022, pp. 69–76.
- [27] 3GPP, “5g; management and orchestration; 5g performance measurements,” ETSI TS, Tech. Rep., 2020.
- [28] K. Zheng, W. Zhao, T. Woodford, R. Zhao, X. Zhang, and Y. Hua, “Enhancing mmwave radar sensing using a phased-mimo architecture,” in *Proceedings of the 22nd Annual International Conference on Mobile Systems, Applications and Services*, 2024, pp. 56–69.
- [29] F. Campolo, A. Blaga, M. Rea, A. Lozano, and X. Costa-Pérez, “5gnss: Fusion of 5g-nr and gnss localization for enhanced positioning accuracy and reliability,” *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, 2024.
- [30] O-RAN Alliance, “WG3, E2 Service Model (E2SM) KPM (O-RAN.WG3.E2SM-KPM-R003-v04.00),” Tech. Rep., 2023.
- [31] A. García-Saavedra and X. Costa-Perez, “O-ran: Disrupting the virtualized ran ecosystem,” *IEEE Communications Standards Magazine*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 96–103, 2021.
- [32] S. D’Oro, M. Polese, L. Bonati, H. Cheng, and T. Melodia, “dapps: Distributed applications for real-time inference and control in o-ran,” *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 60, no. 11, pp. 52–58, 2022.
- [33] O-RAN next Generation Research Group (nGRG), “dapps for real-time ran control: Use cases and requirements,” Contributed Research Report, Tech. Rep., 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://mediastorage.o-ran.org/ngrg-rr/nGRG-RR-2024-10-dApp%20use%20cases%20and%20requirements.pdf>
- [34] X. Foukas, B. Radunovic, M. Balkwill, and Z. Lai, “Taking 5g ran analytics and control to a new level,” in *Proceedings of the 29th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking*, 2023, pp. 1–16.
- [35] G. Dahlquist and A. Björck, *Numerical methods*. Courier Corporation, 2003.
- [36] RISE-6G, “RISE network architectures and deployment strategies analysis: final results,” H2020-ICT-52/RISE-6G/D2., Tech. Rep., 2023.
- [37] srsRAN, “Open-source 4g and 5g software radio suites developed by software radio systems.” [Online; accessed 21-Nov-2024]. [Online]. Available: <https://www.srsran.com/>
- [38] O-RAN Alliance, “O-RAN SC (I Release),” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://lf-o-ran-sc.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/REL/pages/12812314/I+Release>
- [39] G. Zhang, D. Zhang, Y. He, J. Chen, F. Zhou, and Y. Chen, “Multi-person passive wifi indoor localization with intelligent reflecting surface,” *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 6534–6546, 2023.
- [40] C. Li, Q. Huang, Y. Zhou, Y. Huang, Q. Hu, H. Chen, and Q. Zhang, “Riscan: Ris-aided multi-user indoor localization using cots wi-fi,” in *Proceedings of the 21st ACM Conference on Embedded Networked Sensor Systems*, 2023, pp. 445–458.
- [41] S. Gezici and H. V. Poor, “Position estimation via ultra-wide-band signals,” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 386–403, 2009.
- [42] J. Zhang, P. V. Orlik, Z. Sahinoglu, A. F. Molisch, and P. Kinney, “Uwb systems for wireless sensor networks,” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 97, no. 2, pp. 313–331, 2009.
- [43] L. Taponneco, A. A. D’Amico, and U. Mengali, “Joint toa and aoa estimation for uwb localization applications,” *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 10, no. 7, pp. 2207–2217, 2011.
- [44] W. Njima, M. Chafii, A. Chorti, R. M. Shubair, and H. V. Poor, “Indoor localization using data augmentation via selective generative adversarial networks,” *IEEE access*, vol. 9, pp. 98 337–98 347, 2021.
- [45] G. Encinas-Lago, F. Devoti, M. Rossanese, V. Sciancalepore, M. Di Renzo, and X. Costa-Pérez, “Coloris: Localization-agnostic smart surfaces enabling opportunistic isac in 6g networks,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.07377*, 2024.
- [46] C. A. Balanis, *Antenna theory: analysis and design*. John Wiley & sons, 2015.
- [47] R. J. Mailloux, *Phased array antenna handbook*. Artech House, 2017.
- [48] J. He, H. Wymeersch, T. Sanganpuak, O. Silven, and M. Juntti, “Adaptive beamforming design for mmwave ris-aided joint localization and communication,” in *2020 IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference Workshops (WCNCW)*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [49] J. He, H. Wymeersch, L. Kong, O. Silvén, and M. Juntti, “Large intelligent surface for positioning in millimeter wave mimo systems,” in *2020 IEEE 91st Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2020-Spring)*, 2020, pp. 1–5.
- [50] A. Fascista, A. Coluccia, H. Wymeersch, and G. Seco-Granados, “Ris-aided joint localization and synchronization with a single-antenna mmwave receiver,” in *ICASSP 2021 - 2021 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, 2021, pp. 4455–4459.
- [51] T. Ma, Y. Xiao, X. Lei, W. Xiong, and Y. Ding, “Indoor localization with reconfigurable intelligent surface,” *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 161–165, 2021.
- [52] K. Keykhosravi, B. Denis, G. C. Alexandropoulos, Z. S. He, A. Albanese, V. Sciancalepore, and H. Wymeersch, “Leveraging ris-enabled smart signal propagation for solving infeasible localization problems: Scenarios, key research directions, and open challenges,” *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 20–28, 2023.
- [53] H. Zhang, H. Zhang, B. Di, K. Bian, Z. Han, and L. Song, “Towards ubiquitous positioning by leveraging reconfigurable intelligent surface,” *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 284–288, 2021.
- [54] D.-R. Emenonye, H. S. Dhillon, and R. M. Buehrer, “Ris-aided localization under position and orientation offsets in the near and far field,” *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 22, no. 12, pp. 9327–9345, 2023.
- [55] T. Ma, Y. Xiao, X. Lei, and M. Xiao, “Integrated sensing and communication for wireless extended reality (xr) with reconfigurable intelligent surface,” *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing*, vol. 17, no. 5, pp. 980–994, 2023.
- [56] M. Asif Haider, Y. D. Zhang, and E. Aboutanos, “Isac system assisted by ris with sparse active elements,” *EURASIP Journal on Advances in Signal Processing*, vol. 2023, no. 1, p. 20, 2023.
- [57] Z. Wu, Y. Li, X. Zhang, X. Meng, X. Lv, and Y. Wu, “Multiple anchors and ris-aided localization method in complex nlos environments,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2024.
- [58] G. Wu, H. Chen, X. Zhao, H. Liu, and J. You, “Accuracy estimation of multi-ris assisted positioning in indoor uwb system,” *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, 2024.
- [59] R. Zhao, T. Woodford, T. Wei, K. Qian, and X. Zhang, “M-cube: A millimeter-wave massive mimo software radio,” in *Proceedings of the 26th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking*, 2020, pp. 1–14.
- [60] K. M. Bae, N. Ahn, Y. Chae, P. Pathak, S.-M. Sohn, and S. M. Kim, “Omniscatter: extreme sensitivity mmwave backscattering using commodity fmcw radar,” in *Proceedings of the 20th Annual International Conference on Mobile Systems, Applications and Services*, 2022, pp. 316–329.
- [61] Z. Yang, C. Wu, and Y. Liu, “Locating in fingerprint space: Wireless indoor localization with little human intervention,” in *Proceedings of the 18th annual international conference on Mobile computing and networking*, 2012, pp. 269–280.
- [62] K. Yang, Y. Chen, and W. Du, “Orchloc: In-orchard localization via a single lora gateway and generative diffusion model-based fingerprinting,” in *Proceedings of the 22nd Annual International Conference on Mobile Systems, Applications and Services*, 2024, pp. 304–317.
- [63] A. Blaga, F. Campolo, M. Rea, and X. Costa-Pérez, “3dsar+: A single-drone 3d cellular search and rescue solution leveraging 5g-nr,” *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, 2024.
- [64] A. Albanese, V. Sciancalepore, and X. Costa-Pérez, “Sardo: An automated search-and-rescue drone-based solution for victims localization,” *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 21, no. 9, pp. 3312–3325, 2021.
- [65] A. Blanco, P. J. Mateo, F. Gringoli, and J. Widmer, “Augmenting mmwave localization accuracy through sub-6 ghz on off-the-shelf devices,” in *Proceedings of the 20th Annual International Conference on Mobile Systems, Applications and Services*, 2022, pp. 477–490.
- [66] P. Gertzell, J. Landelius, H. Nyqvist, A. Fascista, A. Coluccia, G. Seco-Granados, N. Garcia, and H. Wymeersch, “5g multi-bs positioning with a single-antenna receiver,” in *2020 IEEE 31st Annual International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–5.
- [67] D. Zhang, Y. Hu, and Y. Chen, “Mtrack: Tracking multiperson moving trajectories and vital signs with radio signals,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 3904–3914, 2020.
- [68] F. Adib, Z. Kabelac, D. Katabi, and R. C. Miller, “3d tracking via body radio reflections,” in *11th USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI 14)*, 2014, pp. 317–329.

- [69] T. Pedersen, B. H. Fleury, and I. COST Action CA15104, “Whitepaper on new localization methods for 5g wireless systems and the internet-of-things,” 2018.
- [70] C. B. Barneto, T. Riihonen, M. Turunen, L. Anttila, M. Fleischer, K. Stadius, J. Ryyänänen, and M. Valkama, “Full-duplex ofdm radar with lte and 5g nr waveforms: Challenges, solutions, and measurements,” *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 67, no. 10, pp. 4042–4054, 2019.
- [71] Y. Dantas, P. E. Iturria-Rivera, H. Zhou, Y. Ozcan, M. Bavand, M. El-sayed, R. Gaigalas, and M. Erol-Kantarci, “Split learning for sensing-aided single and multi-level beam selection in multi-vendor ran,” in *GLOBECOM 2023-2023 IEEE Global Communications Conference*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 6652–6657.
- [72] H. Zhang, Y. Zhang, X. Liu, K. Sun, and Y. Zhang, “Resource allocation and mobility management for perceptive mobile networks in 6g,” *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 2024.
- [73] F. Hamidi-Sepehr, T. Hewavithana, R. Vannithamby, and A. Merwaday, “Integrating sensing into cellular systems: Architectural requirements and performance enhancements,” *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, 2024.
- [74] X. Vilajosana, G. Boquet, J. Melia-Segui, P. Tuset-Peiro, B. Martinez, and F. Adelantado, “Challenges and opportunities for simultaneous multifunctional wireless networks in the uhf band,” *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 5, pp. 48–54, 2023.
- [75] E. C. Strinati, G. C. Alexandropoulos, H. Wymeersch, B. Denis, V. Sciancalepore, R. D’Errico, A. Clemente, D.-T. Phan-Huy, E. De Carvalho, and P. Popovski, “Reconfigurable, intelligent, and sustainable wireless environments for 6g smart connectivity,” *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 59, no. 10, pp. 99–105, 2021.
- [76] X. Ma, S. Guo, H. Zhang, Y. Fang, and D. Yuan, “Joint beamforming and reflecting design in reconfigurable intelligent surface-aided multi-user communication systems,” *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 3269–3283, 2021.
- [77] A. Albanese, F. Devoti, V. Sciancalepore, M. Di Renzo, and X. Costa-Pérez, “Marisa: A self-configuring metasurfaces absorption and reflection solution towards 6g,” in *IEEE INFOCOM 2022-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 250–259.
- [78] A. Albanese, F. Devoti, V. Sciancalepore, M. Di Renzo, A. Banchs, and X. Costa-Pérez, “Ares: Autonomous ris solution with energy harvesting and self-configuration towards 6 g,” *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, 2024.
- [79] H. Zhang, S. Zeng, B. Di, Y. Tan, M. Di Renzo, M. Debbah, Z. Han, H. V. Poor, and L. Song, “Intelligent omni-surfaces for full-dimensional wireless communications: Principles, technology, and implementation,” *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 60, no. 2, pp. 39–45, 2022.

Pau Baguer completed a double engineering degree in aerospace systems and networking from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (Barcelona) in 2023. He joined the AI-driven Systems group of i2CAT in June 2022 and became a junior researcher in 2023. Pau’s research interests are in Open RAN, AI-enhanced systems and smart surfaces.

Josep Xavier Salvat received his Ph.D. from the Technical University of Kaiserslautern in 2022 and he currently works as senior research scientist in the 6G Network group at NEC Laboratories Europe, Heidelberg. He also teaches as a part-time professor at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) in the Dep. He worked as reviewer of several international scientific conferences and journals, including *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, *IEEE ICC*, and *Computer Communications Journal* and has actively participated in several EU-funded projects, including H2020 5Growth, H2020 Daemon and SNS-JU BeGREEN. His research interests lie in the appli-

cation of machine learning to real-life computer communications systems, including resource allocation and energy efficiency problems.

Guillermo Encinas-Lago received his M.Sc. degrees in Applied Physics from Universidad Autónoma de Madrid in 2013 and in Industry 4.0 from Universidad Carlos III de Madrid in 2021, both in Spain, and a Ph.D. in Telecommunications from Université Paris-Saclay, France, in 2024, while employed at NEC Laboratories Europe in Heidelberg, Germany, under the MSCA program. He works now as a senior researcher in i2CAT, focused on reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, machine learning, JCAS, and prototyping.

Placido Mursia received the B.Sc. and M.Sc. (with honours) degrees in Telecommunication Engineering from Politecnico of Turin in 2015 and 2018, respectively. He obtained his Ph.D from Sorbonne Université of Paris, at the Communication Systems department of EURECOM in 2021. He is currently a Senior Research Scientist in the 6GN group at NEC Laboratories Europe in Heidelberg. His research interests lie in wireless communications, convex optimization, signal processing, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, and integrated sensing and communication.

Esteban Municio received the Ph.D. degree from the University of Antwerp, imec, Belgium, in 2020. Then, he joined imec as a Postdoctoral Researcher for two years. Since January 2022, he has been with i2CAT, where currently he is a Research Scientist within the AI-Driven Systems Group. His research interests are in the field of AI-driven programmable open networks, TSN and ultra-reliable Industrial IoT.

Marco Rossanese received the B.Sc. and M.Sc. degrees in Telecommunication Engineering from Università degli Studi di Padova in 2017 and 2019, respectively. He received a Ph.D in computer science from the Technische Universität of Darmstadt. He is employed as a researcher at NEC Laboratories Europe GmbH in the 6G Networks team. He focuses his work on Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS).

Vincenzo Sciancalepore received his M.Sc. degree in Telecommunications Engineering and Telematics Engineering in 2011 and 2012, respectively, whereas in 2015, he received a double Ph.D. degree. Currently, he is a Principal Researcher at NEC Laboratories Europe, focusing his activity on reconfigurable intelligent surfaces. He is an Editor of the *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications* (since 2020) and *IEEE Transactions on Communications* (since 2024).

Xavier Costa Xavier Costa-Pérez is ICREA Research Professor, Scientific Director at the i2cat Research Center and Head of 6G R&D at NEC Laboratories Europe. His team generates research results which are regularly published at top scientific venues, produces innovations which have received several awards for successful technology transfers, participates in major European Commission R&D collaborative projects. He has held multiple leadership positions both in industry and research organizations such as Deputy General

Manager, Chief Researcher, Technology Board member and Scientific Advisory Board Member. As a standards delegate, he contributed to multiple standardization bodies (e.g. IEEE 802.11, 802.16, WiFi Alliance, 3GPP, ...) and was recognized in several standards as a top contributor. He has served on the Organizing Committees of several conferences (including ACM MOBICOM, IEEE INFOCOM, WCNC and Greencom), published papers of high impact and holds about 100 granted patents. He has served as Editor at IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing (TMC), IEEE Transactions on Communications (TCOM) and Elsevier Computer Communications journals (COMCOM). Xavier received both his M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in Telecommunications from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC) in Barcelona and was the recipient of a national award for his Ph.D. thesis.